

Absorption Spectra and Configuration of Copper (II) Formate Complexes with Amines

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Formation of complex compounds between copper(II) formate, ammonia and pyridine has been reported^{1,2}. No detailed work on the subject has so far been done. In the present paper visible absorption measurements, done on a series of complexes prepared with amines are reported. The d-d spectrum of the metal has also been discussed in the light of the structure of the complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

The complexes were prepared by the following three methods which have already been outlined^{3,4}.

A. Gaseous method. B. Reflux method. C. Shaking method.

(1) Biformatobis (amine) copper(II). Prepared by method A is blue in colour. Found Cu=33.3%, N=14.8%; $C_4H_8O_4N_2$. Cu requires Cu=33.8%, N=14.9%.

(2) Biformatobis (methylamine) copper(II). Prepared by method A is light blue in colour. Found Cu=28.9%, N=12.0%; $C_5H_{12}O_4N_2$. Cu requires Cu=29.4%, N=13.6%.

(3) Biformatobis (ethylamine) copper(II). Prepared by method A is blue in colour. Found Cu=25.8%, N=11.0%; $C_6H_{16}O_4N_2$. Cu requires Cu=26.1%, N=11.5%.

(4) Biformatobis (pyridine) copper(II). Prepared by method B is blue in colour. Found Cu=20.1%, N=8.7%; $C_{12}H_{18}O_4N_4$. Cu requires Cu=20.3%, N=8.6%.

(5) Biformatomono (ethylenediamine) copper(II). Prepared by method C is blue in colour. Found Cu=29.6%, N=12.9%; $C_4H_{10}O_4N_2$. Cu requires Cu=29.8%, N=13.1%.

(6) Biformatomono (propylendiamine) copper(II). Prepared by method C and is blue in colour. Found Cu=27.0%, N=12.0%; $C_5H_{14}O_4N_2$. Cu requires Cu=27.9%, N=12.3%.

The visible absorption measurements were done on a Unicam S. P. 500 spectrophotometer in formamide. The results of total base, molecular weight, conductance and spectral maxima are give in the table I.

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TABLE I

No.	Formulae	Percentage of Base		Molecular Weight		Molar conductance in mhos	$\lambda_{\max}$ in $m\mu$
		Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.		
1.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{HCOO})_2(\text{NH}_3)_2]^0$	18.14	18.40	187.5	176	0.3	625
2.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{HCOO})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2)_2]^0$	28.77	28.98	215.5	201	0.5	625
3.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{HCOO})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2)_2]^0$	36.96	36.36	243.5	229	0.4	630
4.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{HCOO})_2(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{N})_2]^0$	50.72	49.98	311.5	320	0.2	630
5.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{HCOO})_2(\text{en})]^0$	28.10	27.86	213.5	221	0.6	670
6.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{HCOO})_2(\text{pn})]^0$	32.52	32.43	227.5	209	0.5	670

In the above table en represents ethylenediamine; pn represents propylenediamine.

DISCUSSION

The analytical results indicate the molecular formulae to be $\text{Cu}(\text{HCOO})_2$, Amine and $\text{Cu}(\text{HCOO})_2 \cdot 2\text{Amine}$. The complexes are non-electrolyte, as the value of conductance is less than one³. The depression of freezing point gives the normal theoretical value of molecular weight.

The complexes dissolve in nitrobenzene and formamide to exhibit the typical deep blue colour characteristic of copper amine complexes. This blue colour is due to the presence of an absorption band in the visible region of the spectrum. The occurrence of the band is due to the splitting of fine 3d levels. In the ground state i.e. in absence of any field the configuration is $(t_{2g})^6(eg)^3$ and in excited state it is $(t_{2g})^5(eg)^4$. The position of absorption maxima for tetraquocopper (II) sulphate in water is 800 $m\mu$ while that of tetramino-copper(II) sulphate is 590 $m\mu$. The amine as it produces a stronger field causes the absorption band to move from far red to the middle of the red region of the spectrum. According to Bjerrum⁶ it is the cis-isomer for which the maxima is at 670 $m\mu$ and for trans at 630 $m\mu$.

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